

A Quantum-Safe Implementation of the NETCONF protocol

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Abstract—The Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF) is a network management protocol for devices that facilitates the retrieval and uploading of configuration information using YANG data models in a manner closely aligned with their native operational behaviour. IETF describes and standardizes this protocol, covering the transport and security considerations. This paper explores the integration of Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) technologies into the NETCONF protocol by adapting an open-source implementation to support PQC-enabled Transport Layer Security (TLS).

Index Terms—NETCONF, PQC, TLS

I. INTRODUCTION

The primary goal of cryptography is to offer secure communication by providing confidentiality, integrity, and authentication, even in the presence of potential adversaries. However, Cryptographically Relevant Quantum Computers (CRQC) represent a significant future risk to traditional cryptographic mechanisms. CRQC are advanced computational devices that operate based on the principles of quantum mechanics, leveraging properties such as superposition and entanglement to perform specific calculations exponentially faster than classical computers. This capacity compromises traditional algorithms, such as those based on RSA and ECC, due to their ability to efficiently solve problems like integer factorization and discrete logarithms using algorithms such as Shor's.

The identified risk presented by the future existence of these computers has prompted the upgrade of network protocols. This paper analyzes one of the most relevant protocols used in network management, NETCONF, and evaluates its migration to a quantum-safe solution.

A. Network Configuration Protocol

The Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF) is a management network protocol developed and standardized by IETF [1]. Its operations are based on the Remote Procedure Call (RPC) paradigm, where the messages are encoded using either Extensible Markup Language (XML) or JavaScript

Object Notation (JSON) [2]. The protocol allows both parties of the communication, server and client, to be identified and to establish a secured logical session. It is divided into four layers: Secure Transport Layer, Messages Layer, Operations Layer and Content Layer. This research focuses on the Secure Transport Layer, which will be the point of interest throughout the project. NETCONF can be carried out on any transport protocol with the following requirements: shall indicate the session type, provide a persistent connection, support authentication, ensure data integrity and confidentiality, and offer replay protection. The standard recommends the implementation with Transport Layer Security (TLS) RFC5246 [3] or Secure Shell (SSH) RFC4251 [4].

B. Quantum-Safe Cryptography technologies

Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) technology has been developed as a countermeasure to the latent risk from CRQC. Its main purpose is to develop cryptographic systems that enhance traditional cryptography, being resistant to quantum and classical computers. PQC focuses on developing new public-key algorithms based on mathematical problems, addressing key exchange and digital signatures (SIGs). Key Exchange Mechanisms (KEMs) allows the creation of a shared secret key known by both parties. The same key for encryption and decryption of the content will be used to maintain the security principles of communication, message integrity, and confidentiality during the communication. Digital signatures are typically used to authenticate both parts of the communication.

In August 2024, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), who has been working on standardizing PQC algorithms, has published the regulation of key generator and key exchange algorithms:

- **ML-DSA** [5] (Module-Lattice-Based Digital Algorithm) is a SIG scheme with a security based on Module Learning With Errors (MLWE) and Short Integer Solution

(SIS) problems. It offers robust protection by ensuring data integrity, authenticating the signatory’s identity, and providing non-repudiation. The scheme comprises three primary algorithms: 1) a key generation algorithm that, given a random seed, deterministically produces a public-private key pair encoded as byte strings; 2) a signing algorithm that takes a private key, a message, and an optional context string as inputs to generate an encoded signature; and 3) a verification algorithm that uses the corresponding public key, message, and context string to output a Boolean value indicating the validity of the signature. Three parameter sets—ML-DSA-44, ML-DSA-65, and ML-DSA-87—are defined to accommodate different security levels.

- **SLH-DSA** [6] (Stateless Hash-Based Digital Signature Algorithm) is a post-quantum signature scheme constructed from two core hash-based primitives: the Forest of Random Subsets (FORS) and the eXtended Merkle Signature Scheme (XMSS). The design achieves robust protection against tampering and reliably verifies signer authenticity. In SLH-DSA, the key pair is derived from a large collection of FORS key instances, and the authentication of these keys is performed via XMSS signatures. Furthermore, the standard specifies 12 approved parameter sets that combine two hash-function families (SHA-2 and SHAKE), two variants (‘s’ for a smaller signature size and ‘f’ for faster performance), and three distinct security levels.
- **ML-KEM** [7] (Module-Lattice-Based Key-Encapsulation Mechanism) is currently the only post-quantum KEM standard approved by NIST. The scheme is built on the assumed complexity of the MLWE problem. In ML-KEM, a public-key encryption (PKE) scheme derived from the MLWE problem is transformed into a KEM via the Fujisaki–Okamoto transform. A differential aspect of this key exchange mechanism is that it implements the Number-Theoretic Transform (NTT), obtaining high-speed multiplication of polynomials.

The above-listed PQC algorithms are being explored for integration into secure transport protocols across various TCP/IP stack layers, such as MACsec at layer 2, IPsec at layer 3, and TLSv1.3 at layers 5-7. In this study, we have selected NETCONF as a representative protocol due to its widespread adoption in Software-Defined Networking for network management and its potential importance in early post-quantum cryptography migration efforts within management systems.

II. QUANTUM SECURE ARCHITECTURE

A. NETCONF Classical Data Flow

Traditional NETCONF architecture is presented in Figure 1. The NETCONF client (network manager) starts two different sessions to reply to the server’s running configuration to two different NETCONF servers (network device). The request operation `<get-config>` is encoded as an `<rpc>` element in XML format, and the server responds `<rpc-reply>` hold the information into the `<data>` element.

Fig. 1. NETCONF protocol scenario.

In detail, the first step involves establishing a TLS security layer where both parties in the communication are authenticated using digital certificates, i.e. asymmetric cryptography. A secure communication channel is then created using symmetric encryption for data exchange. TLS secures all transmitted traffic, including transport-protocol-independent RPCs, which are structured according to a YANG data model and serialized in formats such as XML or JSON.

The RPC-based communication model works with `<rpc>` and `<rpc-reply>` elements. When the client sends an `<rpc>` element to the server, it must include the “message-id” as a normalized XML attribute; the `<rpc-reply>` is the server’s response and must also include the same “message-id” If an error occurs, the reply must contain a `<rpc-error>` element; otherwise, the `<data>` will contain the requested information. The notification data has been standardized in the YANG data modeling language for the NETCONF protocol, as specified in RFC 6020 [8], and formatted in XML. This standard specifies all data sent between a NETCONF client and server, following a hierarchical scheme: modules and submodules.

The NETCONF protocol supports the following operations:

- `<get>`: Retrieves both configuration and state (operational) data from the device.
- `<get-config>`: Retrieves configuration data from a specified datastore.
- `<edit-config>`: Adds, modifies, or deletes elements within a specified configuration datastore.
- `<copy-config>`: Replaces the contents of a target datastore with those from a source datastore.
- `<delete-config>`: Removes a specified non-running configuration datastore, such as startup or candidate.
- `<lock>`: Locks a specific configuration datastore to prevent modifications by other clients.
- `<unlock>`: Releases a previously locked configuration datastore.
- `<close-session>`: Closes an active NETCONF session initiated by the client, releasing associated resources.
- `<kill-session>`: Terminates another active session forcefully, releasing associated resources.

The requirements specified in the RFC 7589 to the NETCONF protocol over TLS with mutual X.509 authentication [9] are, for a TLS 1.2 version:

- The NETCONF client acts as a TLS client, who must send a ClientHello message to initialize the TLS handshake.

- The NETCONF server acts as a TLS server, has to respond with a *ServerHello* message, a *CertificateRequest* message, and sends its server certificate.
- The NETCONF client verifies the server identity and responds with its certificate and *ClientKeyExchange*.
- The NETCONF server, if using Diffie-Hellman/ECDHE, sends the *ServerKeyExchange*.
- Server decrypts the pre-master secret.
- Once verified, both parts of the communication generates a Shared Secret Key to establish a secured cipher communication.
- Finished the TLS handshake the client and the server start the exchange NETCONF messages.

In turn, the RFC 7589 document defines as 6513 as the default TCP port number with service name “netconf-tls”.

B. NETCONF Quantum-Safe Data Flow

Despite the security measures outlined previously, the cryptographic methods used in TLS 1.2 are vulnerable to attacks by CRQC and will require the transition to PQC ones.

The proposed solution replaces the traditional TLS NETCONF implementation with TLS version 1.3 (TLSv1.3), which offers improvements in terms of speed and security over previous versions. Additionally, the PQC solution aims to integrate Quantum-safe Certificate, Public and Private keys generated by a Post-Quantum provider into the NETCONF YANG data modeling, as well as KEM methods. The sequence of messages implemented in TLSv1.3 handshake are:

- **Key Exchange Messages:** Offers information of the security server and client capabilities, establishing shared secrets. The *ClientHello* message specified: a list of available cipher suites, a list of KEMs, a list of accepted SIG algorithms and a list of preshared keys for preferred cipher. If the server supports the algorithm and parameters, a *HelloRetry* is not required. The server responds with a *ServerHello* which contains, among others, a 32B random sequence and the agreed-upon cipher.
- **Server Parameters:** After the *ServerHello* message, the *EncryptedExtensions* and *CertificateRequest* is specified.
- **Authentication Messages:** The server and client sends its certificates, the *CertificateVerify* (optional) and the *Finished* messages verify the agreed keys, adding a Message Authentication Code (MAC) of the entire handshake.

III. QUANTUM-SAFE NETCONF IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation and evaluation of pre-standardized PQC algorithms in the NETCONF scenarios have been made in our laboratory employing the following settings: 32 x Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5218 CPU @ 2.30GHz, 56 GB of RAM, 16 cores and 8 TB of storage. Within this infrastructure, two virtual machines are configured as client and server with 8.00 GiB RAM memory, 2 processor sockets, 64 GB of storage and Ubuntu 22.04.5 live-server. The Virtual Machine (VM) that works as NETCONF server has IPv4 address 10.22.101.110 and work with TCP 6513 port, the Client VM has IPv4 address 10.22.101.116.

The incorporation of Quantum Resistant Cryptography based on the recommendations of the NIST has been obtained using the OQS provider developed by Open-Quantum Safe organization. To obtain a correct integration has been found to be necessary work with:

- OpenSSL version release 3.3.0.
- LibOQS from OQS project.
- OQS-Provider from OQS project.

The LibOQS [10] is a open-source C library for PQC algorithms, which installation offers PQC KEM and SIG algorithms into the system. To obtain a fully PQC establishment in TLSv1.3 it is required to add *oqsprovider* [11] in the list of available providers. For this, it is necessary to export the installed libraries properly and modify the *openssl.cnf* file “*openssl.cnf*”. In addition to this setting, the Client virtual machine also requires the *liboqs-python* [12] implementation that provides 7 post-quantum-resistant signature algorithms as ML-DSA, and Falcon, among others, along with their Elliptic Curve Cryptography p256 and RSA-3072 hybrid versions, and KEM methods as FrodoKEM, BIKE, ML-KEM and HQC.

On the other hand, the NETCONF server has been implemented in C language with *Netopeer* server tool-set [13], developed by the CESNET [14]:

- YANG-based configuration and operational state data store for Unix/Linux applications, *sysrepo* [15].
- YANG data modeling language library, *libyang* [16].
- C NETCONF library, *libnetconf2* [17].
- NETCONF server toolset, *netopeer2*.

The NETCONF client has been implemented in Python language with *ncclient* [18] NETCONF implementation. Figure 2 shows the architecture assembled in the laboratory.

Once the experimental environment has the PQC cryptography extension and each one of the original NETCONF programs, it is necessary to modify the source code of *libnetconf2*, *netopeer2* and *ncclient* to extend its functionality to work with PQC. Then the server and client are able to interpret the PQC certificates and perform the handshake with PQC KEM algorithms. For the PQC implementation, the main modifications have been the integration of *SSL-CTX* [19] data type “*libctx*” object, created as a framework to establish TLS/SSL enabled connections. This object holds several relevant configuration and data to SSL/TLS establishment, loading and enabling into “*libctx*” the “*default*” and “*oqsprovider*” providers. As well, it has been required to modify the *libnetconf2*’s encoding/decoding functions to be able to read and work with digital certificates and public/private keys generated by quantum-safe SIG algorithms.

Regarding the NETCONF client, *ncclient*, has been necessary to work with the *ncclient* source code, since the OQS module has to be manually incorporated in the TLS module. After making these changes and recompiling the source codes of each software employed, the NETCONF server and client were interoperable over the PQC-enabled TLS channel.

Fig. 2. NETCONF Laboratory scenario.

IV. QUANTUM-SAFE NETCONF RESULTS

In these experiments, Self-signed Certificate Authority (CA) and manual certificate distribution are used in our controlled lab environment as a replacement for a quantum-safe Public Key Infrastructure (PKI).

Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Group	Info
10.22.101.116	10.22.101.110	TLSv1.3	1992	kyber1024	Client Hello
10.22.101.110	10.22.101.116	TLSv1.3	4162	kyber1024	Server Hello, Change Cipher Spec
10.22.101.110	10.22.101.116	TLSv1.3	614		Application Data, Application Da
10.22.101.116	10.22.101.110	TLSv1.3	4162		Change Cipher Spec, Application
10.22.101.116	10.22.101.110	TLSv1.3	724		Application Data, Application Da

Fig. 5. Quantum-Safe NETCONF handshake TLSv1.3.

```

SR: Triggering "ietf-netconf-server" "done" event on enabled data.
LN: Listening on 0.0.0.0:830 for SSH connections.
LN: Listening on 0.0.0.0:6513 for TLS connections.
SR: Triggering "ietf-keystore" "done" event on enabled data.
SR: Triggering "ietf-truststore" "done" event on enabled data.
SR: Triggering "ietf-netconf-acm" "done" event on enabled data.
LN: Accepted a connection on 0.0.0.0:6513 from 10.22.101.116:46566.
LN: Libnetconf2: Created OSSSL_LIB_CTX.
LN: Libnetconf2: Loaded default provider.
LN: Libnetconf2: Loaded oqsprovider.
LN: Libnetconf2: Oqsprovider available.
LN: Libnetconf2: TLS SERVER METHOD CORRECTLY.
LN: Loading server certificate and private key correctly.
LN: Certificate's header correctly
LN: Oqsprovider loaded correctly.
LN: New bio created correctly.
LN: New bio writted correctly.
LN: Certificate parse correctly.
LN: Loading server CA correctly.
LN: CA certificates configured.
LN: Server CRL configured: (null).
LN: Cert verify CTN: entry with a matching fingerprint found.
LN: Cert verify CTN: new client username recognized as "tls-test".
LN: Client certificate verified.
NP: Generated new event (netconf-session-start).
NP: Session 1: thread 2 event new RPC.
NP: Session 1: thread 1 event new RPC.
NP: Session 1: thread 1 event session terminated.
NP: Generated new event (netconf-session-end).

```

Fig. 3. NETCONF server's response.

```

OpenSSL version: OpenSSL 3.3.0 9 Apr 2024
NETCONF connection established successfully.
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?><data xmlns="urn:ietf:params:xml:ns:
netconf:base:1.0"><keystore xmlns="urn:ietf:params:xml:ns:yang:ietf-keysto
re"><asymmetric-keys><asymmetric-key><name>genkey</name><public-key-format
xmlns:ct="urn:ietf:params:xml:ns:yang:ietf-crypto-types">ct:ssh-public-ke
y-format</public-key-format><private-key-format xmlns:ct="urn:ietf:params:

```

Fig. 4. NETCONF client's response.

Figure 3 and 4 show each network element logs once the system is activated and communicating with the new TLSv1.3 Falcon-512 SIG algorithm and Kyber-1024 key exchange method with the OQS provider.

Performing a more in-depth analysis, Figure 5 shows the TLS handshake process carried out between both network components. It is observed that, the Open-Quantum Safe integration

into OpenSSL is success, as well, the implemented protocol is TLSv1.3 as defined in Libnetconf2. Also, it confirms that working with the TLSv1.3 version achieves a considerable reduction in the exchange of messages thus obtaining better communication setup times. At the same time, working with PQC keys and certificates, the sizes of these are considerably higher compared to those obtained with traditional algorithms.

TABLE I
TLSV1.3 HANDSHAKE SET-UP TIME METRIC (MS)

KEM Method	Security Level	Time (ms)
X25519	Traditional	116.172
RSA	Traditional	114.030
Kyber-1024	5	115.835
Kyber-768	3	114.030
P521_Kyber-1024	5	130.696
ML-KEM-1024	5	87.515
ML-KEM-768	3	81.704
P521_ML-KEM-1024	5	104.147
Bikel-5	5	415.700
Bikel-3	3	199.455
P521_Bikel-5	5	427.114
Frodo-1344-AES	5	104.669
Frodo-976-AES	3	109.227
P521-Frodo-976-AES	3	134.009

Table I shows the geometric average by performing ten time handshake measurements for each KEM, where the time of establishing the connection from the Controller (Client) to the Agent (Server) is measured by the *manager.connect-tls()* function offered by ncclient. In order to isolate the comparative as much as possible, all measurements have been made with the same configuration of certificates and keys, and exclusively the Group element in "openssl.cnf" has been modified.

After evaluating these measurements, it has been concluded

that the most optimal method recommended by NIST is the ML-KEM family, whose key exchange times are considerably lower than the rest of PQC methods, achieving key exchange times very similar to those offered by traditional algorithms. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that hybrid methods considerably slow down the handshake.

TABLE II
TLSV1.3 HANDSHAKE PACKET LENGTH (kB)

KEM Method	Client Hello (kB)	Server Hello (kB)
X25519	0.583	3.162
RSA	0.583	3.165
Kyber-1024	1.992	4.162
Kyber-768	1.596	4.162
P521_Kyber-1024	2.113	4.162
ML-KEM-1024	1.97	4.162
ML-KEM-768	1.572	4.162
P521_ML-KEM-1024	2.113	4.162
Bikel-5	5.534	5.315
Bikel-3	3.495	4.162
P521_Bikel-5	5.665	5.448
Frodo-1344-AES	7.457	7.3181
Frodo-976-AES	1.540	1.425
P521-Frodo-1344-AES	7.590	7.451

Table II represents the “Client Hello” and “Server Hello” packet’s length. Taking into account that in each measurement is working with the same certificates and private/public key, it can be concluded that a NIST high strength security level involves a higher client’s hello length packet. The server hello message’s length is constant for most methods. Besides, the Frodo-1344-AES and its hybrid version P521-Frodo-1344-AES, require fragmentation of the messages due to the increase in the size of the key-shares parameter.

Operators should consider previous network-related aspects when selecting PQC algorithms to manage a network with NETCONF. For instance, a longer handshake duration can significantly slow provisioning orders or monitoring events, especially in large networks with hundreds of devices. Another example is the potential impact on network devices (e.g., firewalls) caused by packet fragmentation that may arise during the handshake process.

TABLE III
CERTIFICATE GENERATOR TIME METRIC (MS) FOR DIFFERENT DIGITAL SIGNATURE ALGORITHMS

Signature	Level	CA (ms)	Priv Key (ms)	CRT (ms)
ED25519	1	9.791	7	8.464
ML-DSA44	1	10.29	7	9.933
Falcon512	1	13.896	21.223	13.564
ML-DSA87	5	11.166	7	10.096
Falcon1024	5	19.295	46.9	18.898

Table III and Table IV show the generation time and size of the self-signed Certification Authority (CA), the certificate (CRT) and private key process for the NETCONF server, using advanced cryptographic signature algorithms aligned with NIST references: ML-DSA and Falcon. It also compares these with the traditional ED22519 algorithm, concluding that the best response with PQC algorithms is achieved with ML-

TABLE IV
CERTIFICATE GENERATOR SIZE METRIC (kB) FOR DIFFERENT DIGITAL SIGNATURE ALGORITHMS

Signature	Level	CA (kB)	Priv Key (kB)	CRT (kB)
ED25519	1	0.753	0.119	0.729
ML-DSA44	1	5.709	5.336	5.685
Falcon512	1	2.744	3.036	2.715
ML-DSA87	5	10.43	10.235	10.410
Falcon1024	5	4.791	5.636	4.771

DSA-87, reaching relatively small key generation values and very close to the times obtained with traditional methods, with a five security level. It is worth mentioning that space storage should be considered a relevant factor in future migrations to PQC (see Table IV) in case a high number of devices are involved in the network management with NETCONF.

Fig. 6. NETCONF server’s CPU consumption.

Fig. 7. NETCONF client’s CPU consumption.

Figure 6 and 7 show the analysis of client and server CPU consumption during the NETCONF connection and the server’s delivery (<get-config>) of a predefined configuration. It has been selected a representative set of algorithms to evaluate the impact of working with different security connection scenarios, level 3 and 5 as AES-192 and AES-256: ED25519,

Falcon-512, Falcon-1024, Mayo-3 and Mayo-5; and KEM methods, X25519, RSA, ML-KEM-768, ML-KEM-1024 and P521_ML-KEM-1024. The server’s CPU consumption metrics show slight differences between working with traditional or PQC SIG algorithms, having higher values for Mayo SIG family algorithm than Falcon and greater CPU consumptions for the level 5 algorithms within each family. Focusing on the KEM scenarios, it is concluded a proper result for PQC KEM methods, ML-KEM level 3 and 5, against worst consumptions in the ML-KEM hybrid case. The client’s CPU consumption shows lower values than the server due to the fact that this service has less complexity. Its metrics shows quite similar consumptions for the traditional and quantum-safe scenarios for the different SIG and KEM methods. The memory consumption measurements show no significant variations with respect to the KEM method being implemented, with only slight variations observed in relation to the SIG used.

TABLE V
TLS OVERHEAD METRICS.

Total (%)	X25519	ML-KEM-1024	P521_ML-KEM-1024
ED25519	5.524	-	-
Falcon-1024	-	10.369	11.598
Mayo-5	-	9.328	9.842

Table V displays the ratio of the TLS handshake message sizes over the total TCP/IP flow sizes. The measured overhead for a secure NETCONF session upgraded from the classical security level 1 to a PQC or hybrid level 5 significantly impacts bandwidth consumption (it doubles it). On the contrary, the results suggest that using hybrid KEM mechanisms over pure PQC KEM is useful because it does not generate a significant increase in traffic bandwidth and could be considered for a conservative quantum-safe transition strategy.

V. CONCLUSIONS

NETCONF is a widely extended network protocol today, thanks to its support by standards. An initial implementation approach has been presented to demonstrate and evaluate the transition towards PQC algorithms associated with the TLSv1.3 protocol. Several open-source software and libraries have been adapted and combined to support this transition.

The high number of devices using NETCONF protocol, especially in complex networks such as telecom operators or network providers, will require long migration and early adoption of the emergent PQC technology that can be used to address the CRQC risk for network protocols. This study demonstrates that the impact will be acceptable and the transition viable thanks to the TLSv1.3 support. Moreover, the measurements in this study can help the network operator design the transition path, considering aspects such as systems resource consumption or impact on the network traffic.

An additional insight gained during the assessment is that the TLS protocol compatibility between classical and PQC during the handshake negotiation has the risk of downgrading the algorithms to classical ones if one of the endpoints is

not PQC compatible. One possible solution is to adopt a different TCP port assignment for a PQC-based exclusive service, such as a “netconf-tls-pqc”, where NETCONF servers will be configured to support only PQC or hybrid KEM and SIGs algorithms.

The authors plan to extend their research by integrating PQC algorithms into alternative transport protocols, such as the Secure Shell (SSH) protocol in NETCONF or into the twin protocol RESTCONF, followed by a comparative analysis of the outcomes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Enns, M. Bjorklund, J. Schoenwaelder, and A. Bierman, “Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF),” RFC 6241, 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6241>
- [2] L. Lhotka, “JSON Encoding of Data Modeled with YANG,” RFC 7951, Aug. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc7951>
- [3] E. Rescorla, “The Transport Layer Security (TLS) Protocol Version 1.3,” RFC 8446, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc8446>
- [4] R. Enns, M. Bjorklund, J. Schoenwaelder, and A. Bierman, “The Secure Shell (SSH) Protocol Architecture,” RFC 4251, 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc4251>
- [5] N. I. of Standards and Technology, “Fips 204: Module-lattice-based digital signature standard,” 2024, accessed: 2025-02-06. [Online]. Available: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/FIPS/NIST.FIPS.204.pdf>
- [6] —, “Fips 205: Stateless hash-based digital signature standard,” 2024, accessed: 2025-02-06. [Online]. Available: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/FIPS/NIST.FIPS.205.pdf>
- [7] —, “Module-lattice-based key-encapsulation mechanism standard,” 2024, accessed: 2025-02-06. [Online]. Available: <https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/FIPS/NIST.FIPS.203.pdf>
- [8] M. Bjorklund, “YANG - A Data Modeling Language for the Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF),” RFC 6020, 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6020>
- [9] J. S. M. Badra, A. Luchuk, “Using the NETCONF Protocol over Transport Layer Security (TLS) with Mutual X.509 Authentication,” RFC 7589, 2015. [Online]. Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/rfc7589/>
- [10] Open Quantum Safe, “liboqs,” GitHub repository, accessed: 2025-02-11. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/open-quantum-safe/liboqs>
- [11] —, “Oqs provider,” GitHub repository, accessed: 2025-02-11. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/open-quantum-safe/oqs-provider>
- [12] M. Baentsch, C. Paquin, R. Levitte, B. Hess, and J. Segeth, “liboqs-python: Python 3 bindings for liboqs,” <https://github.com/open-quantum-safe/liboqs-python>, 2023.
- [13] N. Project, “Netopeer2 – netconf server,” <https://github.com/CESNET/netopeer2>.
- [14] CESNET, “Cesnet website,” <https://www.cesnet.cz/>.
- [15] sysrepo, “sysrepo: Yang-based configuration and operational state data store for unix/linux applications,” <https://github.com/sysrepo/sysrepo>.
- [16] CESNET, “libyang: Yang data modeling language library,” <https://github.com/CESNET/libyang>.
- [17] —, “libnetconf 2: C netconf library,” <https://github.com/CESNET/libNETCONF.2>.
- [18] ncclient, “ncclient,” <https://pypi.org/project/ncclient/>, Oct. 2024.
- [19] O. Project, “Openssl documentation (v3.3),” 2023, accessed: 2025-02-07. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.openssl.org/3.3/>